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**DEVELOPMENT OF EFFORTS IN VARIOUS DEPARTMENTS
OF SHIVAJI UNIVERSITY KOLHAPUR IN 2010-2011**

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Abstract:

The backbone of Education at all levels is a teacher. Teacher plays innumerable roles for a student at different times and different things. Teacher is seen a source of knowledge, professional knowledge, transmitter, buffer between a student and alien domains of knowledge, a receiver of new information in his subject, a philosopher and guide to slow learners, gifted learners and so on. Teacher is also a representative of the certifying authority for a diploma or a degree or a board examination, who is directly in contact with a student on a regular basis. Thus it is radically important to constantly monitor the health of this link between a student and his goal – Education. The process that reliably monitors the health through teacher's performance usually on a yearly basis is called the appraisal. Different countries have evolved appraisal procedures according to their educational patterns, needs and social structure. Perhaps a scheme that works successfully in the U.S or U.K. may not prove successful in India since our country is full of diversity and contradictions that are seldom faced by western countries. Hence it is felt that it is necessary to evolve an appraisal scheme that does not turn a blind eye to realities faced by the Indian society.

Keywords- *Learning, Research etc.*

Introduction:

A great deal of deliberation goes on in the western world and even books are published¹ on issues related to the appraisal of teachers at school level particularly in the last two decades. These books might be useful in knowing the philosophical basis or the core values on which

appraisal of teachers is done in many countries. However, the author believes that the exact duplication of such efforts in India is neither possible nor desirable. The vast expanse of the country has led to an equally vast system of Education even if we restrict ourselves to the system of formal education. We have Lakh of schools, thousands of colleges and hundreds of Universities, which are catering to a variety of people from the poorest to the richest, located in areas from deserts to forests using more two dozen languages and dialects. All this makes it virtually impossible to even imagine a system that can successfully meet the diverse needs of our country. That is why one is slowly induced to realize that it is more meaningful to create a tailor-made system of appraisal according to local needs, constraints and availability of human resources.

Teachers are well familiar with assessment and evaluation of students. Self appraisal helps to figure out what teacher's strengths and weaknesses are. It allows one to take an honest look at oneself. It is a process of self evaluation to determine the level of self-efficiency. It is a part of continuing professional development or career advancement. It has been suggested as an indicator of CAS. As per UGC regulations 2010 on minimum qualifications for appointment of teachers and other academic staff in universities and colleges it is mandatory for all universities and colleges to prepare Performance Based Appraisal in the prescribed format for applying to any teaching post or career advancement. So the author has to criticize the learning and research in various departments of Shivaji University annual report of 2011-2012.

Objectives:

The study aims at the following objectives

- 1 To find out department wise Teaching Staff in the year 2010-2011 in Shivaji University Kolhapur.
2. To find out the department wise Research Publications Teaching Staff in the year 2010-2011 in Shivaji University Kolhapur.
3. To find out the department wise Book Publications Teaching Staff in the year 2010-2011 in Shivaji University Kolhapur

4. To identify the department wise Paper Presented in Conference/Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop of Teaching Staff in the year 2010-2011 in Shivaji University Kolhapur
5. To identify the department wise Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop organized by the Department in the year 2010-2011 in Shivaji University Kolhapur

TABLE No. 1

Department wise Teaching Staff

Sr. No	Departments	Total number of Teaching Staff
1	Chemistry	18
2	Biochemistry	9
3	Physics	11
4	Electronics	7
5	Botony	16
6	Zoology	10
7	Geography	10
8	Mathematics	10
9	Statistics	4
10	Computer Science	9
11	Environment	7
12	Industrial Chemistry	3
13	Agrichemistry and Keed management	3
14	Biotechnology	4
15	Microbiology	3
16	Food Science & Technology	2
17	Technology	6
18	B-Tech	6
19	USIC Department	2

20	Engineering	8
21	Marathi	5
22	Hindi	4
23	Foreign Language	5
24	History	5
25	Economics	9
26	Sociology	6
27	M.S.W	5
28	Politics	5
29	Journalism and Communication	4
30	M.A. Mass Communication	13
31	Library and Information Science	7
32	Education	6
33	Adult and Continuing education and extension work	4
34	Commerce and Management	6
35	Law	4
36	Music and drama Department	4
37	Women's study Centre	4
38	Internet Unit	3
39	Gandhi's study Centre	1
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	1
41	Bhagwan Mahaveer Adhyasan	6
42	M.B.A Department	5
43	Distance education Centre	5
44	Nehru study Centre	1

45	Social Ddeprived and Inclusive Policy study centre	2
46	Community Development Centre	1
47	Shahu Research Centre	4
48	Applied chemistry Department	4
Total		277

Analysis and Interpretation

Table No.1 shows that total number of departments in Shivaji University is 48. There are 38 departments and 10 centers. Total numbers of teaching staff are 277 worked in various departments. Department of chemistry have highest teaching staff. Gandhi’s study centre, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and development centre, Nehru study centre and community development centre have only one teaching staff.

TABLE No. 2

Department wise Projects of Teaching Staff

Sr. No	Departments	Total no of Projects		
		Major	Minor	Total
1	Chemistry	12	1	13
2	Biochemistry	-	-	Nil
3	Physics	6	-	6
4	Electronics	3	-	3
5	Botany	12	1	13
6	Zoology	5	-	5
7	Geography	1	5	6
8	Mathematics	-	1	1
9	Statistics	-	-	Nil
10	Computer Science	-	2	2

11	Environment	6	1	7
12	Industrial Chemistry	1	-	1
13	Agrichemistry and Keed Management	-	-	Nil
14	Biotechnology	-	-	Nil
15	Microbiology	-	-	Nil
16	Food Science and Technology	2	-	2
17	Technology	3	1	4
18	B-Tech	2	-	2
19	Usic Department	-	-	Nil
20	Engineering	-	-	Nil
21	Marathi	4	-	4
22	Hindi	-	-	Nil
23	Foreign Language	-	-	Nil
24	History	-	2	2
25	Economics	-	-	Nil
26	Sociology	3	2	5
27	M.S.W	-	-	Nil
28	Politics	2	1	3
29	Journalism & Communication	1	-	1
30	M.A. Mass Communication	1	-	1
31	Library & Information Science	-	1	1
32	Education	2	3	5
33	Adult and Continuing education and extension work	-	-	-
34	Commerce & Management	1	2	3
35	Law	-	-	Nil
36	Music and drama Department	-	-	Nil
37	Women's study Centre	1	-	1
38	Internet Unit	-	-	Nil

39	Gandhi's study Centre	1	-	1
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	2	-	2
41	Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan	-	-	Nil
42	M.B.A Department	-	-	Nil
43	Distance education Centre	-	12	12
44	Nehru study Centre	-	1	1
45	Social Deprived and Inclusive Policy study centre	-	-	Not mentioned amount
46	Commu. Development Centre	-	-	Nil
47	Shahu Research Centre	-	-	Two Research project sanctioned in S.U.Kolhapur
48	Applied chemistry Department	-	-	Nil
Total		107		

Analysis and Interpretation

Table No. 2 Shows that department wise various major & minor project works is done. In chemistry department and microbiology department 13 project is carried within 2010-2011. In all projects major project is in chemistry and microbiology (i.e.12) is maximum and Geography , Industrial Chemistry, Journalism and Communication, M.A. Mass Communication, Commerce & Management, Women's study Centre, Gandhi's study centre is minimum. In Shahu Research Centre two research projects is sanctioned under Shivaji University Kolhapur

In all minor project Distance education Centre have maximum minor project and Chemistry, Botany, Mathematics, Environment, Technology, Politics, Library and Information Science and Nehru study centre is only one minor project. In some department such as Biochemistry, Statistics, Agriculture Chemistry and keed management, Biotechnology, Microbiology, Usic Department , Engineering department, Hindi department, Foreign language

department, Economics department, M.S.W. department, M.A. Mass communication department, Adult and Continuing educational department, Law department, Music and drama department, Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan, M.B.A Department, Nehru study centre, Community. Development Centre and Applied chemistry Department there is no project is done.

TABLE No. 3

Department wise Research Publications

Sr. No	Departments	Research Publications
1	Chemistry	73
2	Biochemistry	47
3	Physics	170
4	Electronics	28
5	Botany	102
6	Zoology	60
7	Geography	20
8	Mathematics	07
9	Statistics	14
10	Computer Science	-
11	Environment	11
12	Industrial Chemistry	13
13	Agrichemistry and Keed	19
14	Biotechnology	23
15	Microbiology	16
16	Food Science & Technology	10
17	Technology	07
18	B-Tech	21
19	USIC Department	04
20	Engineering	17
21	Marathi	17

22	Hindi	17
23	Foreign Language	03
24	History	04
25	Economics	29
26	Sociology	11
27	M.S.W	-
28	Politics	08
29	Journalism and Communication	01
30	M.A. Mass Communication	01
31	Library & Information Science	-
32	Education	11
33	Adult & Continuing education	-
34	Commerce & Management	08
35	Law	01
36	Music and drama Department	-
37	Women's study Centre	01
38	Internet Unit	-
39	Gandhi's study Centre	02
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	03
41	Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan	-
42	M.B.A Department	02
43	Distance education Centre	03
44	Nehru study Centre	03
45	Social Deprived and Inclusive Policy study centre	01
46	Communication Development Centre	-
47	Shahu Research Centre	1
48	Applied chemistry Department	16
Total		805

Analysis and Interpretation

Table no. 3 shows that research publication in various departments. In the subject physics there is maximum (i.e. 170) research publications are done. In computer science, Adult & Continuing education, Music and drama department, Internet unit centre, Bhagwan Mahavir Adhysan, M.S.W, Library and Information science and Community Development Centre there is no research publication. So there is need to publication.

TABLE No. 4

Department wise Book Publications

Sr. No	Departments	Book Publications
1	Chemistry	
2	Biochemistry	03
3	Physics	-
4	Electronics	-
5	Botany	Published articles in Books-1
6	Zoology	Published articles in Books-1
7	Geography	05
8	Mathematics	Published articles in Books-1
9	Statistics	-
10	Computer Science	-
11	Environment	02
12	Industrial Chemistry	-
13	Agrichemistry & Keed	-
14	Biotechnology	-
15	Microbiology	-
16	Food Science & Technology	-
17	Technology	-

18	B-Tech	-
19	USIC Department	-
20	Engineering	10
21	Marathi	05
22	Hindi	06
23	Foreign Language	-
24	History	-
25	Economics	02
26	Sociology	03
27	M.S.W	-
28	Politics	06
29	Journalism and Communication	-
30	M.A. Mass Communication	-
31	Library & Information Science	-
32	Education	-
33	Adult and Continuing education and extension work	01
34	Commerce & Management	-
35	Law	-
36	Music & drama Department	-
37	Women's study Centre	-
38	Internet Unit	-
39	Gandhi's study Centre	01
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	01
41	Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan	-
42	M.B.A Department	-
43	Distance education Centre	-
44	Nehru study Centre	5
45	Social Deprived and Inclusive Policy	-

	study centre	
46	Community Development Centre	-
47	Shahu Research Centre	01
48	Applied chemistry Department	-
Total		51

Analysis and Interpretation

Table no. 4 shows that published book in various departments. Total number of published books is 51. In English subject maximum 10 books are published. In subject Physics, Electronics, Statistics, Computer Science, Industrial chemistry, Agriculture and keed management, Biotechnology, Botany, Food science & technology, Technology, B-Tech, Usic Department, Foreign language, History, M.S.W, Journalism & Communication science M.A. Mass communication, Library & Information science, Commerce & Management Education, Law, Music & drama department, Women’s study centre, Internet unit centre, Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan, M.B.A department, Distance education centre, Social Vanchitata and Samaveshak Dhoran study centre, Community development centre, Applied chemistry department there are no publication for any books. So there is need to publish the books.

TABLE No. 5

**Department wise Paper Presented in Conference,
Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop**

Sr. No	Departments	Papers Presented in Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop
1	Chemistry	27
2	Biochemistry	34
3	Physics	168
4	Electronics	20
5	Botany	52
6	Zoology	29

7	Geography	19
8	Mathematics	04
9	Statistics	04
10	Computer Science	01
11	Environment	05
12	Industrial Chemistry	09
13	Agrochemistry and Keed management	04
14	Biotechnology	-
15	Microbiology	15
16	Food Science & Technology	-
17	Technology	09
18	B-Tech	08
19	USIC Department	04
20	Engineering	39
21	Marathi	24
22	Hindi	20
23	Foreign Language	10
24	History	20
25	Economics	32
26	Sociology	27
27	M.S.W	04
28	Politics	30
29	Journalism and Communication	06
30	M.A. Mass Communication	08
31	Library and Information Science	06
32	Education	21
33	Adult and Continuing education and extension work	15
34	Commerce & Management	44
35	Law	02

36	Music & drama Department	08
37	Women’s study Centre	01
38	Internet Unit	-
39	Gandhi’s study Centre	13
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	15
41	Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan	-
42	M.B.A Department	10
43	Distance education Centre	02
44	Nehru study Centre	10
45	Social Deprived and Inclusive Policy study centre	03
46	Community Development Centre	-
47	Shahu Research Centre	02
48	Applied chemistry Department	08
Total		792

Analysis and Interpretation

Table no. 5 shows that paper presented in academic conference, seminars, workshop, etc and invited talk. In the subject physics maximum numbers of papers are presented in Conferences, Seminars, Symposium, and Workshop etc. In subject Biotechnology, Food science and technology, Community development centre, Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan , Internet Unit centre papers are not presented in .conferences, seminars, workshops etc. So there is need to publish the paper in Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop.

TABLE No.6

**Department wise in Conference, Seminars/Symposium/
Workshop organized by the Departments**

Sr. No	Departments	Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop organized by the Department
1	Chemistry	01
2	Biochemistry	-
3	Physics	02
4	Electronics	02
5	Botany	13
6	Zoology	-
7	Geography	-
8	Mathematics	01
9	Statistics	01
10	Computer Science	-
11	Environment Science	03
12	Industrial Chemistry	-
13	Agrochemistry and Keed management	02
14	Biotechnology	01
15	Microbiology	-
16	Food Science and Technology	01
17	Technology	06
18	B-Tech	02
19	Usic Department	04
20	Engineering	01
21	Marathi	02
22	Hindi	03
23	Foreign Language	-
24	History	04
25	Economics	-
26	Sociology	01

27	M.S.W	-
28	Politics	13
29	Journalism and Communication	-
30	M.A. Mass Communication	04
31	Library & Information Science	-
32	Education	03
33	Adult and Continuing education and extension work	05
34	Commerce and Management	01
35	Law	01
36	Music and drama Department	-
37	Women's study Centre	01
38	Internet Unit	-
39	Gandhi's study Centre	04
40	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Development Centre	-
41	Bhagwan Mahavir Adhyasan	02
42	M.B.A Department	01
43	Distance education Centre	05
44	Nehru study	15
45	Social Deprived and Inclusive Policy study centre	03
46	Community Development Centre	03
47	Shahu Research Centre	01
48	Applied chemistry Department	-
Total		

Analysis and Interpretation

Table No. 6 shows that departments conducted Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop. Various departments are conducted Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop

such as chemistry departments physics, electronics, mathematics, statistics, environment science, agro chemistry and keed management, biotechnology, food science and technology, Agriculture Chemistry and keed management, Biotechnology, Botany , Usic Department , Engineering department, Hindi department, Marathi ts, History Departments, Sociology departments, Education departments, Commerce and Management, Women's study Centre, Gandhi's study Centre, Distance education Centre, Social Vanchitata and Samaveshak Dhoran study centre, Economics department, M.S.W. department, M.A. Mass communication department, Adult and Continuing education and extension work department, Law department, Music and drama department, Bhagwan Mahaveer Adhyasan, M.B.A Department, Nehru study centre, Community. Development Centre, Microbiology and politics departments are conducted highest workshop, conferences, seminars and symposium. Computer Science, Industrial chemistry, Chemistry, Zoology, Biochemistry, Geography, M.S.W., Microbiology, Foreign language, Economics, Journalism and Communication on science, Library and Information science, Music and drama department, Internet unit cell, Dr. B. A. research and development centre and Applied chemistry department are not arranged any Conference, Seminars, Workshops etc.

Conclusion

The University of Kolhapur has grown exceptionally in case of both students and teachers. In chemistry department and microbiology department 13 project is carried within 2010-2011. In the subject physics there is maximum (i.e. 170) research publications are done. In English subject there are 10 books are published. Various departments are conducted Conference, Seminars/Symposium/ Workshop. In the subject physics maximum numbers of papers are presented in Conferences, Seminars, Symposium, and Workshop. All these activities are arranged in various departments automatically the lecturer improve their appraisal.

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